

Social Networking Practices: Its Influence to the Study Habits of College Students

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Abstract:- This study aimed to determine the Social Networking Practices and Its influence to study habits of BEED 3rd and 4th year students. The study used a descriptive correlational research design that involved the participation of 30 respondents. The result shows that the social networking practices of BEED 3rd and 4th year students were very evident in terms of acquisition of knowledge, netiquette and time management. The study result indicated that most of BEED students were practicing those practices which were helpful to their studies. The rating proves that the influence of social networking in terms of reading skills, comprehension skills and research skills were very evident to the study habits of BEED 3rd and 4th year students. The result implies that student's use of social networking has influence to their study habits. The null hypothesis (Ho1) of the study was accepted. The results indicated that there is no significant difference on the social networking practices when the respondents were grouped according to sex. We conclude that through our findings, social networking practices in terms of acquisition of knowledge, netiquette and time management has influence in terms of reading, comprehension and research skills to the study habits of BEED 3rd and 4th year students.

Keywords:- Social Networking Practices, Study habits, Acquisition of knowledge, Netiquette, Time Management, Reading skills, Comprehension skills, Research skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social Networking is most important topic nowadays. It is not only about posting something or getting updates of any places or thing but also for knowing other people from different places for work regarding personal and professional life (Kenton, 2022).

Social Networking Practices is a term used to describe the different ways in which people create, establish, maintain, or break real world connections with other individuals through electronic communication technologies (Jones, 2020). By this means, some authors claim that they have the ability to improve undergraduate students' involvement and knowledge through the promotion of Collaborative learning (Pulido et. al 2020).

The web had a profound effect on the ways people interact, with online networks arguably playing an important role in changing or augmenting how we connect with others. However, uptake of online social networking by the academic community varies, and needs to be understood. The issues related to social networking practices and study habits into such as technologies and the underlying

relationships between their advantages and drawbacks is lacking. There were issues with privacy and the blurring of lines, lack of credibility, and the quality of the content provided, time constraints, excessive self-promotion by others, plagiarism, and the risk of endangering one's career; necessity to use social networking; and vulnerability to being targeted (Lupton, 2014). Although it is only one example and may have limitations due to sampling, Lupton's analysis gives a more complete and balanced view of online academic networking.

In the Philippines, the advent use of technology using the internet became the frontier of daily communication, collaboration and networking. This frontier is delineated by many social networking websites and portals. The study was conducted at Lyceum of the Philippines- Laguna. The result of the study showed a statistically significant positive relationship between time spent by students on SNSs and their Academic performance. The higher the time they spent on SNS, the lower is the time they spent on studying. Thus, the study found out that SNSs usage had no significant relationship on student academic performance (Marquez, 2014). The improvement in the grades relies on other factors within the teaching-learning process and could not be attributed to the use of SNS alone.

In a local setting, the students of Notre Dame of Midsayap College utilize different social networking sites like Zoom, Schoology and ClassIn particularly when taking online classes. In order to know if students' study habits were influenced by Social networking, the researchers will attempt to determine it by means of conducting this study particularly among BEED students in their third and fourth years.

II. RELATED LITERATURE

This research presents the gathered researches from different sources. These studies will used as a guide support to our research in relation to Social Networking Practices: Its Influence to study habits of 3rd and 4th year students at Notre Dame of Midsayap College.

A. Social Networking Practices in terms of Acquisition of Knowledge

Many academics have emphasized the importance of Collaborative Learning and its potential to improve academic performance and empowerment. This is possible if students' needs and formative assessment are prioritized, and a community classroom is established to encourage student participation, improve academic performance, and manage knowledge exchange. In this regard, social networking sites are extremely beneficial for forming academic groups and

improving students' academic performance (Pulido et al., 2020).

Students utilize social networking sites for a variety of reasons, including exchanging opinions, gathering information, amusement, self-documentation, self-expression, and social connections (Alhabash & Ma, 2017; Chawinga, 2017; Lemay et al., 2020). (Smith, 2017; Hoi, 2021; Raza et al., 2020). Accessing course content, arranging group work, receiving comments, and communicating with instructors have all been documented in the literature (Al-Qaysi et al., 2021; Al-Rahmi et al., 2020; Ansari & Khan, 2020; Hoi, 2021; Raza et al., 2020; Smith, 2017).

According to Permana's (2018) research, social media can be used as a learning resource since it promotes growing critical and creative thinking abilities by raising motivation, critical thinking skills, and creative thinking abilities.

Integrating social networking in learning and teaching environment has been shown to generate new forms of inquiry, communication, collaboration, and work identity, as well as have positive cognitive, social, and emotional effects (Greenhow & Lewin, 2019).

According to Brown (2022), he stated that “Acquiring Knowledge and skill and having them steadily available from memory so you can make sense of future problems and opportunities”. One may argue that learning to play guitar has little to do with understanding future difficulties or opportunities. There is still a lot of disagreement regarding what knowledge is and how we get it.

The use of Social networking has become an integral part of intellectual work, and students posting study-related material on social networking platforms are considered a reliable source of information that is important to each community, such as those of students, customers, and employees (Pekkala et.al 2022). The users of social networking (computational technology that helps to develop and share ideas, perceptual knowledge, professional interests, information, and other expressions through social network platforms) may read or see their friends' activities online without direct contact with them (Sutherland & Jalali, 2017). Furthermore, social networking sites utilize features, such as comments, postings, digital photographs, video-sharing, and data about online interactions, that provide vitality for social networking users.

B. Social Networking Practice in terms of Netiquette

Netiquette is an online term used for internet etiquette guidelines which explain how to act while online using digital formats. Netiquette is a necessary component to becoming a digital citizen, which is a person able to use technology to interact well with other people in society. According to Shea (2011), the ten core rules of netiquette include: Remember the human, adhere to the same standards of behaviour online that you follow in real life, know where you are in cyberspace, respect other people's tie and bandwidth, make yourself look good online, share expert knowledge, help keep flame wars under control, respect

other people's privacy, don't abuse your power, and be forgiving of other people's mistake.

Butler (2020) stated that increasingly, K12 educators are seeing the need to only utilize the internet in instruction, but also to teach students the knowledge and critical thinking skills needed to be safe and responsible digital citizens both inside and outside of school. With digital responsibilities comes the need to be appropriate and polite in an effective manner while posting to digital connected services.

In addition, according to Webmaster (2011) Privacy is as important as respecting other people's opinion. He believes that when you respect a person, you allow the person to determine the limit of your involvement in his life. “People that invade others people's privacy are those that have fidgety and unsettled minds”.

C. Social Media Practices in terms of Time Management

Time management is a skill that allows a student to apportion time to various goal-oriented tasks that are important for academic adjustment, according to Mohamed, Hamal and Mohamed (2018). Students participate in a variety of activities at a typical university community, such as the University of Uyo. Academic duties, personal social commitments, and other extracurricular activities are all examples of these activities. A student who is unable to devote a sufficient amount of time to these activities may find it difficult to adjust academically and socially (Mercanlioglu, 2010). Nasrullah and Khan emphasize the need of time management (2015) Time is an “indefinitely divisible and useable commodity,” according to the definition. They compared time management to a circumstance in which a person strives to manage his limited resources in order to achieve greater goals. Given the importance of time management in higher education institutions, this term is apt.

At all stages of education, time management is crucial. Nasrullah and Khan (2015), on the other hand, argue that time management skills are more important for adjustment during the years of higher education. This is due to the fact that students in tertiary institutions have a heavier academic word load than those in the earlier stages of their education. Time management skills can be acquired in a variety of ways. Alghaswyneh and Basri (2015) listed scheduling and prioritization as to time management strategies that a learner can employ. A learner can guarantee that limited time is used wisely by using the program time table. Other characteristics expected of a student with time management skill include goal setting, reduced procrastination, and achievement motivation (Mohamed et al., 2018).

One research of students aged 12 to 23 found that individuals who used social networking while studying had a reduced attention span when just studying (Rosen et al., 2013). Furthermore, when students use social media and other smartphone-related features in an absent-minded manner, they may experience an increase in attention related errors (Marty-Dugas et al., 2017). Distractions from technology are more common than ever, including smart phone notifications while driving, working, or in school

(Brown et al., 2019). Technology, especially social media, has the potential to severely impact work and/or school performance.

According to Mingle and Musah (2015), that most respondents in their study experienced negative effects such as poor grammar spelling, late submission of assignments, less study time and poor academic performance. Though part of these studies affirmed some benefits of social media usage in the academic life of students, it is necessary as educators to be concerned about its negative effects which seem to be outweighing the advantages as far as education is concerned in Ghana.

D. Influence of Social Networking Sites to study habits in terms of Reading skill

Reading skills according to the article Indeed (2021),” are abilities that pertain to a person’s capacity to read, comprehend, interpret and decode written language and texts”. Excellent reading abilities can help you understand and respond to written communications such as emails, text messages, letters, and other written message. Comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, and methods that help readers interpret and discover meaning in texts are all parts of reading skills that work together to enhance overall literacy skills.

Reading abilities cover a wide range of abilities that can be used to every aspect of life. Strong reading skills enable you to interpret and find meaning in everything you read, and you may improve your ability to communicate effectively through writing by continually improving these skills (from the article Indeed, 2021).

The study by Karrenbauer and Kovalevskaya (2020) reveals the difficulty of reading articles online that are listed in an aggregated form in a dynamic stream, such as news feeds, as abbreviated social media messages, or in the daily update of new articles on SNS. In this situation, the listing’s brief information about an article just hints at its content. They consider readers who want to get the most out of their information in the shortest amount of time; therefore they either dismiss or read an article based on the suggestion. The reader has the option of continuing with the present article or skipping the remainder of the content indefinitely.

Every day, over one billion learning-related videos are seen on YouTube (YouTube, 2021), and a growing number of specialist learning channels are being created on the network (e.g., Tadbier & Shoufan, 2021). Given the vast amount of films available online about nearly anything and the growing number of Internet-connected devices in classrooms, it’s no surprise that online videos are frequently used in both formal and casual learning (e.g., Bergdahl et al., 2020; Dyosi & Hattingh, 2018; European Commission, 2019; Fleck et al., 2014; Rosenthal, 2018).

E. Influence of Social Networking Sites to study habits in terms of Comprehension skills

Comprehension defined as “Comprehending printed symbols and giving meaning to them.” On the other hand, Polloway, Patton, Serna, et al. (2018) proposed that comprehension is the production of meaning from a given written text based on the coordination of a number of interrelated data sources.

According to Fredrickson (2021), he stated that reading comprehension is comprised of several levels. They are literal, interpretative, critical and creative. Focusing on critical level of comprehension, you’re moving further beyond the text and making judgements as you read. Students at this level make decisions, such as whether the text or author is accurate and reliable, or discern if a statement is a fact or an opinion.

Previous research on false news has found that, rather than partisanship, a lack of thinking can lead to susceptibility to fake news (Pennycook & Rand, 2018, 2019).

Analytical thinking is linked to the ability to distinguish between fake and true news (Pennycook & Rand, 2019). This research showed that media literacy is critical in fighting the spread of fake news on social media platforms.

Bilbao, Donguilla, & Vasay (2016) contested that comprehension is the heart of reading for without such it becomes meaningless and that there are four levels of comprehension: literal, inferential or interpretative, evaluative, and creative. Literal is also called as factual level. It refers to the readers’ ability to decode words, give meaning in a context, and determine word relationship. Learners are as well expected to identify fundamental information and follow basic instructions.

F. Influence of Social Networking Sites to study habits in terms of Research skills

Undergraduate students at Igbinedion University in Nigeria said that they predominantly use mobile phones to search for academic resources and consult scholarly publications for assignments, which is consistent with this finding. They also stated that accessing the internet on their mobile phones allows them to rapidly search for and retrieve academic content (Mamudu and Oyewo, 2020).

YouTube is a free video sharing site with a diverse selection of videos to suit any child’s learning style. From science to phonics, everything is covered. When a YouTube video is used to accompany a tough topic, it can make it easier to understand (Lynch, 2020). YouTube can be a huge help in teaching, regardless of the student’s age. It keeps a child’s attention and is distinct from their teacher, which can help a child listen more effectively.

Based from the definition Research skills (2020) research skills are the ability to search for, find, collect, analyse, interpret and evaluate information that is relevant to the subject being studied. Research shapes the future, it teaches us new things and helps us adapt and evolve.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. *Research Design*

This study used descriptive-correlational research design in conducting the research among 3rd year and 4th year BEED students.

According to Best and Khan (2006), Descriptive Research uses methods to describe what is, describing, recording, analyzing and interpreting conditions that exist. It is descriptive because it described the profile of the respondents particularly the age, sex, year and marital status. It also determined the usage of social networking practices and its influence to study habits among students.

Based on the Rutgers University Libraries, Correlational research attempts to determine whether, and to what degree, a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables using statistical data. It is correlational because it determined the significant difference on the Social Networking Practices when the respondents grouped according to sex.

B. *Locale and Respondents of the Study*

The study was conducted among selected BEED 3rd and 4th year students at Notre Dame of Midsayap College, Poblacion 5, Midsayap, Cotabato. The respondents of the study were 30 BEED 3rd and 4th year students who were enrolled to school year 20212022.

C. *Sampling Design*

The researchers employed the purposive sampling design in selecting the respondents. It is purposive since the respondents were proficient users of social networking sites and currently enrolled in their 3rd and 4th year of BEED at NDMC were eligible to participate in the study.

D. *Research Instrument*

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire as the main source of data. Items included in the instrument were based on the related literature and studies reviewed by the researcher. The questionnaire was composed of four (4) parts.

The first part was about the Demographical profile of the respondents which includes their year, sex, age and their marital status. The respondents only supplied the needed information for the first section of the instrument.

Second part was composed of questions regarding what social networking sites they use and how much time did they spend on using social networking sites in a day.

They will supply answers based on their experience using social networking sites.

The Third part was about Social Networking Practices in terms of Acquisition of Knowledge, Netiquette and Time Management. Items included the questionnaires were sourced out from the statement of the problem. In this part, we rated using the scale 1-5, where; 5- Very Evident 4- Evident , 3- Moderately Evident, 2- A little evident and 1- Not at all.

The Fourth and last part was about the influence of Social Networking Sites to the study habits of students which include the reading skills, comprehension skills and research skills. In this part, we rated using the scale 1-5, where; 5- Very much influence, 4- Influence, 3- Moderately Influence, 2- A little influence and 1- Not at all.

IV. RESULTS

This chapter presents the statistical treatment of data and its interpretation based on the research pursued. The discussion covers the Demographic profile of the respondents of BEED 3rd and 4th year students, Their Social Networking Practices, Influences of Social Networking to study habits and the significant different on Social Networking practices when grouped according to sex.

Table 1 presents the frequency count and percentage distribution of thirty (30) respondents according to age, sex, marital status, year level, Social networking utilized, and number of hours spent on Social Networking.

Profile of the Respondents	f	%
Age		
20	1	3.33
21	8	26.67
22	14	46.67
23	3	10
24 and above	4	13.33
Total	30	100
Sex		
Male	5	16.67
Female	25	83.33
Total	30	100
Marital Status		
Single	29	96.67
Married	1	3.33
Solo parent	0	0
Total	30	100
Year Level		
3 rd year	18	60
4 th year	12	40
Total	30	100
Social Networking utilized		
Google	27	90
Youtube	28	93.33
Facebook	27	90
Twitter	9	30
Instagram	20	66.67
Messenger	27	90
Hours spent in Social Networking		
1-2 hours	2	6.67
3-4 hours	9	30
5-6 hours	13	43.33
7-8 hours	5	16.67
9-more hours	1	3.33
Total	30	100

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondents

A. Age of Respondents

Data show that (3.33%) of the respondents are 20 years of age; (26.67%) are 21 years of age; (46.67%) are 22 years of age and (10%) are 23 years of age, and (13.33%) are 24 years of age and above.

B. Sex of Respondents

Data show that there are greater Female respondents with 83.33 % than Male with 16.67%.

C. Civil status of Respondents

Data show that (96.67%) are Single and (3.33%) are married.

D. Social Networking Used by the Students

Data show that (90%) of the respondents are using Google, (93.33%) are using YouTube, (90%) are using Facebook. (30%) of the respondents are using Twitter, (66.67%) are using Instagram and (90%) of the respondents are using messenger.

E. Hours spent in Social Networking

Data show that (6.67%) spends 1-2 hours a day, (30%) of the respondents are spending 3-4 hours a day, (43.33%) are spending 5-6 hours a day, (16.67%) are spending 7-8 hours a day and (3.33%) of the respondents spends 9 or more hours a day.

Table 2 present the Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation of Social Networking Practices in terms of Acquisition of Knowledge, Netiquette and Time Management.

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
A. Acquisition of Knowledge			
1. I easily learn and process information through social networking sites.	4.27	0.52	Very Evident
2. I am confident with my skills in manipulating social networking sites.	4.30	0.60	Very Evident
3. I use social networking sites for collaborative learning.	4.57	0.63	Very Evident
4. I use social networking sites to seek help from my teachers.	4.57	0.50	Very Evident
5. I use social networking sites to get information regarding current social events.	4.67	0.55	Very Evident
6. I use social networking sites to enhance cognitive skills.	4.60	0.50	Very Evident
7. Social networking site genuinely give and provide ideas.	4.70	0.53	Very Evident
B. Netiquette			
1. I am responsible digital citizen both inside and outside school.	4.67	0.48	Very Evident
2. I adhere the same standards of behavior online that I follow in real life.	4.53	0.63	Very Evident
3. I respect other’s privacy.	4.90	0.31	Very Evident
4. I don’t engage myself in inappropriate activities online. Ex. Online wars, etc.	4.83	0.38	Very Evident
5. I am aware of different threats online.	4.57	0.63	Very Evident
6. I make myself good online.	4.70	0.47	Very Evident
7. I make myself professional when it comes to online usage.	4.80	0.41	Very Evident
C. Time Management			
1. I value my time that I used it accordingly.	4.53	0.51	Very Evident
2. I engage myself in different extra-curricular at the same time doing my academic duties.	4.33	0.61	Very Evident
3. I manage to multi-task my activities.	4.33	0.55	Very Evident
4. I do my activities ahead of time.	4.20	0.55	Evident
5. I don’t get easily distracted in social networking sites.	4.33	0.61	Very Evident
6. I use social networking sites to lessen my time answering my activities.	4.40	0.56	Very Evident
7. I pass my assignments on-time with the help of social networking sites.	4.60	0.50	Very Evident
Overall	4.54	0.52	Very Evident
Scale 1	Range	Description Not at all	
	1.00 – 1.80		
2	1.81 – 2.60	A Little Evident	
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Evident	
4	3.41 – 4.20	Evident	
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very Evident	

Table 2: Social Networking Practices in terms of Acquisition of Knowledge, Netiquette and Time Management

The result show that in Acquisition of Knowledge, item number 7, “*Social networking site genuinely give and provide ideas*” has obtained the highest mean of 4.70 described as very evident and has the standard deviation of 0.53. For the item with the lowest mean, the item number 1, “*I easily learn and process information through social networking sites.*” has obtained the lowest mean of 4.27 described as very evident and a standard deviation of 0.52.

The result show that the item got the highest mean in Netiquette was item no. 3,

“*I respect other’s privacy.*” It has obtained the highest mean with 4.90 and described as very evident. It has the standard deviation of 0.31. For the item with the lowest mean, item no. 2, “*I adhere the same standards of behavior*

online that I follow in real life.” It has obtained the lowest mean with 4.53 and describes as very evident. It has the standard deviation of 0.63.

The results show that in Time Management, the item with the highest mean in item no. 7, “*I pass my assignments on-time with the help of social networking sites.*” with the highest mean of 4.60 and describes as very evident. It has the standard deviation of

0.50. For the item with the lowest mean, item no. 4, “*I do my activities ahead of time.*” It has obtained the lowest mean with 4.20 and describes as evident. It has the standard deviation of 0.55.

Overall result, Social networking practices in terms of Acquisition of skills, Netiquette and Time management got the total mean of 4.54 and has the standard deviation of 0.52 which described as very evident.

Table 3 presents the Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation of Social Networking Influence in terms of Reading, Comprehension and Research skills.

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
A. Reading Skills			
1. It is easy for me to read articles online.	4.40	0.62	Very Much Influence
2. I easily synthesize what I watch.	4.33	0.55	Very Much Influence
3. I can access news through pages using Facebook.	4.43	0.57	Very Much Influence
4. Social networking sites improves my reading skills.	4.57	0.50	Very Much Influence
5. I am fluent in terms of reading messages.	4.50	0.51	Very Much Influence
6. I can decode written languages with the help of social networking sites.	4.50	0.57	Very Much Influence
7. It ables me to find meaning to everything what I read using social networking sites.	4.70	0.47	Very Much Influence
B. Comprehension Skills			
1. I comprehend the news coming from social networking sites if it is fact or fallacy.	4.33	0.48	Very Much Influence
2. I synthesize fact from social networking sites.	4.33	0.55	Very Much Influence
3. I create ideas through understanding the text or article from social networking sites.	4.53	0.51	Very Much Influence
4. I can easily comprehend main idea about the story using social networking sites.	4.43	0.57	Very Much Influence
5. Social networking sites helps me to outline sentence to sentence coming from a specific story.	4.57	0.50	Very Much Influence
6. I feel different emotions when I read stories.	4.50	0.57	Very Much Influence
7. Social networking sites helps me to be critical thinker.	4.57	0.50	Very Much Influence
C. Research Skills			
1. I gather more information through social networking sites.	4.50	0.51	Very Much Influence
2. I consult to YouTube if I have lessons that give me confusion.	4.50	0.57	Very Much Influence
3. I spend more time browsing social networking sites when I have confusing lessons.	4.43	0.50	Very Much Influence
4. I improve my searching skills through social networking sites.	4.57	0.50	Very Much Influence
5. I browse on social networking sites to create ideas.	4.67	0.48	Very Much Influence
6. I like to search information from social networking sites to prove if it is fake or fact.	4.53	0.51	Very Much Influence
7. I use social networking sites as browsing tool when I have hard lessons.	4.77	0.43	Very Much Influence
	4.51	0.52	Very Much Influence

Table 3. Social Networking Influence in terms of Reading Skills, Comprehension Skills and Research Skills.

• Overall

Scale	Range	Description
1	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all
2	1.81 – 2.60	A Little Influence
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Influence
4	3.41 – 4.20	Much Influence
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very Much Influence

The result show that in Reading Skills, the item who got the highest mean was item no. 7, “It ables me to find meaning to everything what I read using social networking sites.” It has obtained the highest mean of 4.70 with the description of very much influence. It has a standard

deviation of 0.47. The item with the lowest mean was item no.

2, “I easily synthesize what I watch.” This item got the lowest mean of 4.33 and still describes as very much influence. It has a standard deviation of 0.55.

The results show in Comprehension Skills, the items with the highest mean were items no. 5 and 7, “Social networking sites helps me to outline sentence to sentence coming from a specific story.” and “Social networking sites helps me to be critical thinker.” it has a mean of 4.57 and described as very much influence. They have the same standard deviation which is 0.50. The items with the lowest mean were items no. 1 and 2, “I comprehend the news coming from social networking sites if it is fact or fallacy.” and “I synthesize fact from social networking sites.” They have the same mean of 4.33 and described as very much influence. They have differed standard deviation which item no. 1 got 0.48 and item no. 2 got 0.55.

The results show that in Research skills the item who got the highest mean was item no. 7, “I use social networking sites as browsing tool when I have hard lessons.” It obtains the highest mean of 4.77 with the description of Very Much Influence. Its standard deviation is 0.43. The item who got lowest mean was item no. 3, “I spend more time browsing social networking sites when I have confusing lessons.” It has a mean of 4.43 and described as very much influence. It has a standard deviation of 0.50.

For their overall result, the total mean of Social Networking Influence in terms of Reading skills, Comprehension skills and Research skills has the total of 4.51 and with the Standard Deviation of 0.52 which describes as very much influence.

The table 4 presents the T-test to find the significant difference on social networking practices when grouped according to sex.

Sex	N	Mean	SD	Df	p - value	Indication	Decision
Male	5	4.65	0.24	28	0.20	NS	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Female	25	4.52	0.19				

Table 4: Significant Difference on the Social Networking Practices When Grouped According to Sex

NS – Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The entry shows the different results in social networking practices when the respondents were grouped into sex. It reveals that there were more female respondents than male. Male has a mean of 4.65 while Female has a mean of 4.52 which results to male with highest mean. Moreover, the Standard deviation for male is 0.24 while the Standard deviation for female is 0.19. It has a distribution frequency of 28. The computed p-value was 0.20. Finally, this value indicates that the difference were not significant therefore the null hypotheses was not rejected.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The most common social networking that BEED students utilized in helping them in their studies is YouTube. As we conduct all the data gatherings, we found out that those social networking practices in terms of acquisition of knowledge, netiquette and time management tremendously helpful to their study habits. Thus, Social networking practices really influenced the study habits of the students in terms of reading skills, comprehension skills and research skills. We conclude that through our results and findings, Social Networking Practices in terms of Acquisition of Knowledge, Netiquette and Time Management has Influence in terms of Reading, Comprehension and Research Skills to the study habits of BEED 3rd and 4th year students.

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